

Pregnenolone

Progesterone

5 α -DHP

DHEA

Androstenedione

Testosterone

5 α -DHT

Estradiol

SI Figure S1: Dose-dependent effects of steroids on root length of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. We here show the effects of pregnenolone (PR), progesterone (PO), 5 α -dihydroprogesterone (5 α -DHP), DHEA, androstenedione (AD), testosterone (TO), 5 α -dihydrotestosterone (5 α -DHT), and estradiol (ER) on the root length of *A. thaliana*. *A. thaliana* wild-type seeds were germinated on MS medium supplemented with these steroids in concentrations between 10 and 30 μ M (only for 5 α -DHP an additional concentration of 60 μ M was used). Root length was determined after 9 days. The figure shows the root length in cm (mean \pm SEM). Statistical differences, indicated by asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$; ** = $p \leq 0.01$; *** = $p \leq 0.001$), were determined by one-way ANOVA and Turkey test.